

Studies on the Decompositions and Reactions of Urea.

Part I. Reactions of Urea with Hydrazines, Aldehydes, Ketones, etc.

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From a study of the literature it appears that the true mechanism of the reactions of urea has in many cases been little studied. The following investigations, while throwing considerable light in this respect, also point to the importance of urea as a convenient source of both ammonia and isocyanic acid, which can be successfully utilised in many reactions and syntheses. The advantages of urea as a source of NH_3 and NHCO are (i) ammonia can be obtained in perfectly dry state; (ii) both ammonia and isocyanic acid can be made to evolve at very high temperatures up to 200° or above; (iii) as they are generated *in situ*, they act in the nascent state and are, therefore, much more reactive.

Reactions of hydrazines with urea have been investigated in the dry state by Pinner (*Ber.*, 1887, 20, 2358), Skinner and Ruhemann (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1888, 47, 550) and others but in aqueous solutions also similar results have been obtained here. The mechanism of the former type of reactions has been supposed to be of the nature of direct condensation of one or two molecules of urea with the base (hydrazine) followed by the splitting of ammonia. The fact that semicarbazide and hydrazine dicarbonamide are obtained by heating hydrazine with urea (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1895, ii, 52, 465) below the decomposition point of the latter in the solid state, appears to support the above mechanism. But, since urea decomposes into ammonia and isocyanic acid much below its melting point in various solvents (such as water, alcohol, glycerine, etc., as can be shown by warming with silver nitrate when AgCNO is produced), it is quite probable that in the above cases as well, hydrazine hydrate acts as a dissociating medium, and the reactions actually take place between the hydrazine base and the isocyanic acid produced under such condition. The fact that hydrazines yield similar products

even in aqueous solutions, lends support to these interpretations of the reactions.

By gradually heating benzaldehyde with urea, Schiff (*Annalen*, 1896, 291, 376) obtained benzylidenecarbamide and by further heating above its melting point (up to 220°) ammonia was split off and benzylidenebiuret was produced. But by simply heating the reactants at 150-60° only, the same compound has been obtained. So the mode of its formation under this latter condition appears to be different. The reaction probably takes place thus:

Since benzylidenecarbamide does not decompose below its melting point (200°), the formation of benzylidenebiuret direct from it with splitting off of ammonia at 150-60° appears to be unlikely.

Reactions of urea with aromatic haloid substitution products appear to have been very little investigated. By the action of alcoholic ammonia on polynitrohalides at high temperatures in sealed tubes, corresponding amines have usually been obtained. It is quite natural to expect that urea, which is an excellent source of ammonia at very high temperatures, should also yield similar products with polynitrohalides. This expectation has been fulfilled.

By similar reactions with nitrophenols, corresponding amines have been obtained in several cases by Kym (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1907, ii, 75, 325). This reaction has been extended to the case of other phenols.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Reactions of Hydrazines and Hydroxylamine with Urea.

Phenylhydrazine hydrochloride and urea.—Phenylhydrazine hydrochloride (1.4 g.), urea (0.7 g.) and water (7-8 c.c.) were heated together on water-bath for 2½ hours; the mixture cooled and the precipitate obtained on rubbing crystallised from alcohol. It melted at 172°; the melting point being not depressed when mixed with a sample prepared from phenylhydrazine hydrochloride and potassium cyanate.

asym-Phenylbenzylhydrazine hydrochloride and urea.—A mixture of *asym*-phenylbenzylhydrazine hydrochloride (2 g.), urea (1.5 g.) and water (10 c.c.) was heated on a water-bath (2-2½ hours). The precipitated semicarbazide was purified by dissolving in chloroform and reprecipitating by ether. It melts at 139-40° (*cf.* Milrath, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 1865).

8-Quinolyldiazine and urea.—8-Quinolyldiazine (1.4 g.) and urea (1.2 g.) were mixed together and heated at 150-60° for ½ hour. The mass, after extraction with warm water and washing with ether, was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 230° (decomp.). Beilstein reports 235° (decomp.). The same compound was obtained by heating the dihydrochloride of 8-quinolyldiazine (1.1 g.) with excess of urea (0.9 g.) in aqueous solution as in the previous cases.

Hydrazine hydrochloride and urea.—A mixture of hydrazine hydrochloride (1.1 g.), urea (2 g.) and water (7-8 c.c.) was refluxed for about 1½ hours. The precipitate, obtained on concentrating the solution, was warmed with ether and crystallised from hot water; m.p. 246° with decomposition. (Hydrazine dicarbonamide).

Hydrazine dicarbonamide was also produced from hydrazine hydrate (1 c. c.) and urea (2 g.) dissolved in water (7-8 c. c.) and heating the mixture for 2½ hours. The solution was then concentrated to a small bulk, when hydrazine dicarbonamide crystallised out.

Hydroxylamine hydrochloride and urea.—Hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1 g.), urea (1 g.) and water (8-9 c.c.) were heated together on water bath for 2 hours. Bubbles of gas evolved from the solution throughout the reaction. The solution gave strong bluish violet coloration with ferric chloride solution, which showed that hydroxyurea was formed but it could not be easily isolated. By dry heating a mixture of the two reactants gradually to about 145°, the mass swelled up and gases were given out with explosive violence. No hydroxyurea could be detected in the solid residue.

Reactions of Aldehydes and Ketones with Urea.

Benzylidencbiuret.—Benzaldehyde (1 g.) and urea (1.2 g.) were heated together at 150-60° (1½ hours) in an oil bath. The melt was then cooled, washed repeatedly with warm water and the light yellow precipitate filtered. It was next washed several times with warm alcohol and was thus obtained as a white powder almost insoluble in water, alcohol and ether. It was crystallised from hot

water, m. p. 270° (decomp.). (Found: N, 21.54. $C_9H_9O_3N_3$ requires N, 21.99 per cent).

4'-(Dimethylamino)-benzylidenebiuret.—An intimate mixture of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (1.4 g.) and urea (1.4 g.) was heated at 160° for about 2 hours. The mass was washed with hot water and filtered, when a yellowish precipitate was obtained. It was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid, charcoaled and reprecipitated with alkali. The precipitate was repeatedly washed with warm alcohol and was obtained as a white powder, m. p. 264° (decomp.). It is insoluble in water, ether and acetone. (Found: N, 23.42. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2N_4$ requires N, 23.92 per cent).

2'-Hydroxybenzylidenebiuret.—A mixture of salicylaldehyde (1 g.), and urea (1 g.) was heated at $150-60^{\circ}$ for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The cold mass was next well-powdered and dissolved in dilute alkali. The filtrate was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and the yellow precipitate washed repeatedly with water and warm alcohol. The light yellow insoluble residue was further purified by redissolving in dilute alkali. The clear filtrate was then charcoaled, reprecipitated with dilute acid and the white precipitate of *2'*-hydroxybenzylidenebiuret thus obtained was further washed with alcohol. It is practically insoluble in water, ether and alcohol and does not melt below 280° . (Found: N, 19.82. $C_9H_9O_3N_3$ requires N, 20.29 per cent).

1-Methylbenzylideneurea.—Acetophenone and urea did not appreciably react under the above conditions. But by carrying out the reaction at higher temperature and for a longer period the desired compound was obtained. Acetophenone (1.2 g.) and urea (1.2 g.) were heated together at $180-85^{\circ}$ for 3-4 hours. The melt was repeatedly extracted with boiling water. The solid residue was powdered, repeatedly washed with ether and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 176° . It is soluble in alcohol and insoluble in water, ether, acids and alkalis. (Found: C, 59.5; H, 6.6; N, 15.20. $C_9H_{10}ON_2, H_2O$ requires C, 60.0; H, 6.65; N, 15.55 per cent).

Diphenylketone and urea did not appreciably react under the above conditions.

Reactions of Aromatic Halogen Compounds with Urea.

2:4-Dinitrobromobenzene and urea.—An intimate mixture of *2:4*-dinitrobromobenzene (1.2 g.) and urea (2 g.) was heated at 200° for about 4 hours. The yellow crystalline mass was well powdered

and repeatedly washed with hot water and crystallised from alcohol as a glistening yellow crystalline mass, m. p. 181-82°, yield 60%. It was found identical with the compound obtained from the above nitro derivative and alcoholic ammonia (Clemm, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1879, *ii.* 1, 175). (Found: N, 22.82. $C_6H_5O_4N_3$ requires N, 22.95 per cent).

The corresponding carbamido derivative, resulting from the direct condensation of the bromo compound with urea was also formed to some extent, but remained undissolved in alcohol. In the case of 2:4-dinitrochlorobenzene, the yield of the amine was 70%.

2:6-Dinitrochlorobenzene and urea.—On heating an intimate mixture of the above chlorobenzene derivative with large excess of urea as in the previous case, 2:6-dinitroaniline was formed, which was separated and purified as before; yellow needles, m. p. 138°, yield 65%. From the corresponding iodo derivative, a 60% yield of the amine was obtained.

3:5-Dinitrobromobenzene and urea yielded 3:5-dinitroaniline, which crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m. p. 158°, yield 30%. (Found: N, 22.90. $C_6H_5O_4N_3$ requires N, 22.95 per cent).

Reactions of Phenols with Urea.

2:6-Dinitrophenol and urea.—An intimate mixture of 2:6-dinitrophenol (1 g.) and urea (2 g.) was heated at 200° for 4-5 hours. The dirty black mass was well powdered, repeatedly extracted with hot water and the residue washed with dilute alkali and crystallised from alcohol as yellow needles, m. p. 138°, yield 45%.

3:5-Dinitrophenol and urea under the above conditions yielded 3:5-dinitroaniline, which was crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m. p. 158°. The yield was very poor.

2:5-Dinitrophenol and urea similarly gave 2:5-dinitroaniline as orange-yellow crystals from alcohol, m. p. 137°, yield 25%. (Found: N, 22.9. $C_6H_5O_4N_3$ requires N, 22.95 per cent).

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